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On the interaction of celestial bodies (clarification of the Law of Universal Gravitation)

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1. Electric charges in a particle

In [2] the solution of Maxwell's equations for an electromagnetic wave is considered and it is shown that one of the solutions of Maxwell's equations in spherical coordinates is a spherical wave, which can be identified with a particle that is both a particle and a wave. This creates a mathematical description of the AND-wave particle, in contrast to the OR-wave particle described by modern quantum physics, which cannot be both at the same time. This particle rotates, this phenomenon is observed (most likely) in experiments and is described as spin - a certain quality of elementary particles that has no analogy in the macroworld. The existence of a rotating AND-wave particle destroys the boundary between the microworld and the macroworld: both worlds can be described by a single classical electrodynamics.

In [1, Chapter 25] the system of Maxwell's equations for electrostatics is considered. In this case, a certain volume V with permittivity is considered ε , in which there are electric charges with density q independent of coordinates. There also exist electric strengths E in it, which in a rectangular coordinate system satisfy the system of Maxwell's equations of the form (where projections are indicated by a subscript):

$$\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} = \frac{q}{\varepsilon}, \quad (4)$$

Let us show that the solution to this system of equations has the form:

$$E_x = e_o \frac{x}{r}, \quad (5)$$

$$E_y = e_o \frac{y}{r}, \quad (6)$$

$$E_z = e_o \frac{z}{r}, \quad (7)$$

where

$$r^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2. \quad (8)$$

Let us now prove that conditions (1-3) are satisfied. We find from (5):

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} = e_o x \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{r} \right) = -e_o x \frac{2}{r^3} y. \quad (9)$$

Likewise,

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} = -\frac{2x}{r^3} e_o z, \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} = -\frac{2y}{r^3} e_o x, \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z} = -\frac{2y}{r^3} e_o z, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x} = -\frac{2z}{r^3} e_o x, \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y} = -\frac{2z}{r^3} e_o y. \quad (14)$$

From (1, 12, 14) we find:

$$\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z} = \frac{2}{r^3} e_o (-zy + yz) = 0. \quad (15)$$

Similarly, from (2, 10, 13) we find:

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (16)$$

Similarly, from (3, 12, 10) we find:

$$\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} = 0. \quad (17)$$

Thus, the solution to Maxwell's equations (1-4) are the strengths (5-7) at a given charge distribution density. We find from (4)

$$\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial x} = e_o \partial \left(\frac{x}{r} \right) / \partial x = e_o \left(\frac{1}{r} + x \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{1}{r} \right) \right) = e_o \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{2}{r^3} x^2 \right).$$

Likewise,

$$\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial y} = e_o \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{2}{r^3} y^2 \right),$$

$$\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} = e_o \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{2}{r^3} z^2 \right).$$

From here and from (4, 8) we find:

$$e_o \left(\frac{3}{r} - \frac{2r^2}{r^3} \right) = \frac{q}{\varepsilon}$$

or

$$e_o = -\frac{qr}{\varepsilon}. \quad (18)$$

The energy density in this volume is equal to

$$W = \frac{\varepsilon}{2} e_o^2 = \frac{q^2 r^2}{2\varepsilon}. \quad (19)$$

Therefore, the charge has energy.

Thus, the charged volume under consideration creates electrical energy and electrical intensity that are unevenly distributed in its volume.

From (1.5,1.6,1.7,1.18) we find the electrical intensity along the radius

$$E_r = \sqrt{E_x^2 + E_y^2 + E_z^2} = e_o. \quad (20)$$

Thus, at any point of a spherical charged body (including on its surface), the electrical intensity is determined by (7).

We find the tension outside a charged body using Gauss's theorem:

$$E_R = \frac{Q}{4\pi\varepsilon R^2}, \quad (22)$$

where Q is the total charge of the body.

2. Mass particles in a massive body

The body is not solid. It can be assumed that the matter consists of mass particles and this assumption does not violate the law of universal gravitation. The motion of a body consisting of mass particles is equivalent to the current of mass particles - the mass current. In [2, Chapter 1] Maxwell's equations for gravitomagnetism are considered - the Maxwell-Heaviside system of equations for gravitomagnetic waves:

$$\operatorname{div} E_g = -\rho_g / \varepsilon_g, \quad (1)$$

$$\operatorname{rot} E_g = -\frac{1}{c_g} \frac{\partial B_g}{\partial t}, \quad (2)$$

$$\operatorname{div} B_g = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\operatorname{rot} B_g = -\mu_g J_g + \frac{1}{c_g^2} \frac{\partial E_g}{\partial t}, \quad (4)$$

where

ε_g - gravitational permittivity,

μ_g - gravitomagnetic permeability,

E_g - gravitoelectric field strength,

H_g - gravitomagnetic field strength,

B_g - gravitomagnetic induction,

J_g - mass current density,

ρ_g - mass density,

c_g - the speed of the traveling gravitomagnetic wave.

Next we will consider a special case of these equations, when there are no changes in all functions over time:

$$\operatorname{div}E_g = -\rho_g/\varepsilon_g, \quad (5)$$

$$\operatorname{rot}E_g = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$\operatorname{div}H_g = 0, \quad (7)$$

$$\operatorname{rot}H_g = -J_g. \quad (8)$$

This system of equations is analogous to Maxwell's system of equations for direct electric current [1, Chapter 5]. The current in these equations is the mass current discussed at the beginning, J_g

It is easy to see that equations (1.1-1.4) are equivalent to equations (5, 6). In what follows, we will not indicate the subscript g and will write down the solution of the gravitomagnetism equations (5, 6), completely analogous to the equations for the electric field:

$$E_x = e_o \frac{x}{r}, \quad (9)$$

$$E_y = e_o \frac{y}{r}, \quad (10)$$

$$E_z = e_o \frac{z}{r}, \quad (11)$$

where

$$r^2 = x^2 + y^2 + z^2, \quad (12)$$

$$e_o = -\frac{mr}{\varepsilon}, \quad (14)$$

m - mass density.

The gravitational tension created by a body with mass M , at a distance R , is equal to (by analogy with (1.22)) M

$$E_R = \frac{GM}{R^2}, \quad (16)$$

Where

$$G = \frac{1}{4\pi\varepsilon}. \quad (17)$$

We have obtained the law of universal gravitation as a consequence of solving the Maxwell-Heaviside equations. It is important to note that the configuration of the body does not matter.

Let us now consider equations (7, 8) in expanded form:

$$\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial z} = -J_x, \quad (A/m^2) \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial x} = -J_y, \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial H_x}{\partial y} = -J_z, \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial H_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (24)$$

We will look for a solution to this system of equations in the form:

$$H_x = h_x \frac{x}{r}, \quad (25)$$

$$H_y = h_y \frac{y}{r}, \quad (26)$$

$$H_z = h_z \frac{z}{r}. \quad (27)$$

By analogy with (1.9)

$$\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial y} = -\frac{x}{r^3} h_x y. \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_x}{\partial z} = -\frac{x}{r^3} h_x z, \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial x} = -\frac{y}{r^3} h_y x, \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_y}{\partial z} = -\frac{y}{r^3} h_y z, \quad (32)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial x} = -\frac{z}{r^3} h_z x, \quad (33)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_z}{\partial y} = -\frac{z}{r^3} h_z y. \quad (34)$$

From (21, 34, 32) we find:

$$\frac{z}{r^3} h_z y - \frac{y}{r^3} h_y z = -J_x, \quad (35)$$

Similarly, from (22, 30, 33) we find:

$$\frac{x}{r^3} h_x z - \frac{z}{r^3} h_z x = -J_y, \quad (36)$$

Similarly, from (23, 12, 10) we find:

$$\frac{y}{r^3} h_y x - \frac{x}{r^3} h_x y = -J_z. \quad (37)$$

From (35-37) we get:

$$\frac{zy}{r^3} (h_z - h_y) = J_x. \quad (38)$$

$$\frac{xz}{r^3} (h_x - h_z) = J_y, \quad (39)$$

$$\frac{xy}{r^3} (h_y - h_x) = J_z. \quad (40)$$

From (24-27) we get:

$$(h_x + h_y + h_z) = 0. \quad (41)$$

From (38-41) we obtain:

$$(J_x + J_y + J_z) = 0. \quad (42)$$

3. Energy flows

We obtained electro-gravitational (gravitational) strengths in Section 1 and magneto-gravitational strengths in Section 2. According to Maxwell's equations, it follows that there must be flows of electro-magneto-gravitational energy - gravitational energy even in the case when these strengths do not change in time. For electrical engineering, this issue is discussed in detail in [1, Chapter 5], where electric and magnetic strengths are proportional to electric currents. In gravitomagnetism, everything is similar and there are mass currents.

The energy flux densities along the coordinates are determined by the formula (see also (12) in [1, chapter 5])

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_x \\ S_y \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} = (E \times H) = \begin{bmatrix} E_y H_z - E_z H_y \\ E_z H_x - E_x H_z \\ E_x H_y - E_y H_x \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

or, taking into account formulas (2.9-2.11, 2.25-2.27),

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} e_o \frac{y}{r} h_z \frac{z}{r} - e_o \frac{z}{r} h_y \frac{y}{r} \\ e_o \frac{z}{r} h_x \frac{x}{r} - e_o \frac{x}{r} h_z \frac{z}{r} \\ e_o \frac{x}{r} h_y \frac{y}{r} - e_o \frac{y}{r} h_x \frac{x}{r} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{r} e_o \begin{bmatrix} yz(h_z - h_y) \\ xz(h_x - h_z) \\ xy(h_y - h_x) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

From (2, 2.38-2.40) we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{r} e_o \begin{bmatrix} yz \frac{r^3}{zy} J_x \\ xz \frac{r^3}{xz} J_y \\ xy \frac{r^3}{xy} J_z \end{bmatrix} = r^2 e_o \begin{bmatrix} J_x \\ J_y \\ J_z \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

Let us consider the energy flows on the surface of the body at a distance R from the center of coordinates. Taking into account (2.14), we have:

$$S_R = \begin{bmatrix} S_x \\ S_y \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} = -\frac{m}{\varepsilon} R^3 \begin{bmatrix} J_{xR} \\ J_{yR} \\ J_{zR} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Obviously, the energy flows on the surface of a spherical body with radius R above the center of coordinates should be determined by the same formula in spherical coordinates (ρ, φ, θ) :

$$S_R = \begin{bmatrix} S_\rho \\ S_\varphi \\ S_\theta \end{bmatrix} = -\frac{m}{\varepsilon} R^3 \begin{bmatrix} J_{\rho R} \\ J_{\varphi R} \\ J_{\theta R} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

Since the mass of a spherical body

$$M = \frac{4}{3}\pi m R^3 \quad (6)$$

That

$$S_R = \begin{bmatrix} S_\rho \\ S_\varphi \\ S_\theta \end{bmatrix} = -\frac{3M}{4\pi\varepsilon} \begin{bmatrix} J_{\rho R} \\ J_{\varphi R} \\ J_{\theta R} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

So, we have found gravitational energy flows on the surface of the sphere, which are caused by mass currents. But why do these currents appear? To answer this question, we must return to Newton's third law.

Every action has an equal and opposite reaction, in other words, the interactions of two bodies with each other are equal and directed in opposite directions. He spoke of action and reaction, not of forces. Followers reduced the meaning to action and reaction of forces only.

How can this law be interpreted in this case? Let the initial action be the motion of the satellite. The response of the Sun will be the motion of the Sun or the motion of mass currents on the Sun. But for the sake of convenience we will still call this the motion of the Sun.

It is shown above that mass currents create (eventually) a flow of energy, or rather, a part of the energy that is capable of moving. It starts moving, because energy cannot be motionless, it can only be in a flow. It moves to where it can continue moving. It moves to the energy consumer. The energy flow moves together with the force that will do work in the energy consumer - in the satellite.

In a satellite, the work of the force is that it moves the mass currents of the satellite and thereby moves the satellite. The mass currents of the satellite create a flow of energy, which (as in the previous case) moves the Sun.

So, the initial action (the movement of the satellite) caused a response action (the movement of the Sun), which caused the movement of the satellite, and so on.

Here some explanations are required and consequences emerge.

1) The solution of Maxwell's equations for a spherical wave gives an amazing result: energy flows are directed to where there is an energy consumer. This is an absolutely mathematical result without any admixture of reasoning about the physical meaning. However, this result has a clear physical interpretation: the energy flow in a radiating spherical body occurs where there is an energy consumer opposite it (along the radius). (If there

are several consumers, then the total radiation energy is distributed in the same way as the consumers are located.)

2) The Sun's radiation is uneven. The Sun illuminates and warms the planets, but does not waste its energy in Space.«Earthreceives less than 0.5×10^{-9} from the Sun from the energy of its radiation" -writes Wikipedia. However, the electromagnetic radiation of the Sun into the surrounding space cannot be as intense as the radiation to the Earth (otherwise the Sun would have gone out long ago). The Sun radiates only in the direction where there is an energy consumer.

3) Force moves only with the flow of energy. The force of attraction is distributed according to Newton's first law, but it only really appears where there is a body on which it can act. We come to a certain point not to measure tension, but to bring this tension, i.e. force, upon ourselves.

4) The interaction of celestial bodies occurs through the exchange of gravitational energy flows. However, this term is not even used in celestial mechanics.

5) Energy flows from a spherical antenna propagate in the form of an electromagnetic cylindrical wave and do not weaken with distance [1, chapter 1]. Thus, it can be assumed that the energy flow densities from a spherical body are determined at a distance R by formula (7).

6) The density of kinetic energy of a satellite at unit mass

$$W = \frac{v^2}{2}. \quad (8)$$

Using Umov's formula, we find the energy flux density of the satellite at the current moment

$$S_c = \frac{v^3}{2}. \quad (9)$$

In the process of interaction with the Sun, the satellite exchanges with it a flow of energy that changes the kinetic energy of the satellite. Consequently, the density of this exchange flow of energy,

$$S_W = \frac{dW}{dt}. \quad (10)$$

Potential energy density of the satellite

$$Q = \frac{GM}{r}, \quad (11)$$

where

r – the distance between the Sun and the planet,

M - the mass of the Sun,

G – gravitational constant.

In the process of interaction with the Sun, the satellite also exchanges with it a flow of energy that changes the potential energy of the satellite. Consequently, the density of this exchange flow of energy,

$$S_Q = \frac{dQ}{dt}. \quad (12)$$

Thus,

$$S_\rho = S_Q + S_W. \quad (13)$$

Let's take another look *energy constant*

$$h = 2(W - Q). \quad (14)$$

This value is not constant, which is considered in [3].

The illustration above means that a planet falling into the Sun sends a flow of gravitational energy to the Sun together with a force directed toward the Sun and which is currently considered to be the force of attraction emanating from the Sun. In this case, the planet moves in the direction of this force and loses its energy. A planet rotating around the Sun receives a flow of gravitational energy together with a centrifugal force. In [3], the interaction of these two forces is described, due to which the planet is kept in orbit. There it is shown that two ways of describing the orbit of a satellite are possible:

- the first method, currently used and using only the force of gravity,
- the second method, proposed by the author, uses only the force of gravity and centrifugal force, as both real forces.

Both lead to the same result. But the second method allows us to justify the stability of the satellite's elliptical orbits. For example, the relative difference between the found solution and the known one is for the orbit of Mercury and for the speed of movement along the orbit $\delta < 10^{-4}$.

The above allows us to assert that in celestial mechanics it is necessary to use the concept of the transfer of energy interactions through gravitational energy flows. Energy flows, as energy carriers, were introduced into science by Umov and Poynting. It is unacceptable to talk about the energy of interactions and remain silent about how it is transferred, even if this method has not been discovered.

4. About potential energy

Umov's concept is universally recognized, according to which energy must have a material carrier, the flow of which is a flow of energy - energy does not freeze in some place, there is a flow of energy that has the speed of its carrier. Poynting proved that the carrier of electromagnetic energy is an electromagnetic wave. It was shown above that there must be a flow of gravitational energy and its carrier must be a gravitomagnetic wave. This issue is considered in more detail in [6].

But the body contains potential energy. Physics does not ask the question of what is the carrier of this energy. In [1] it is proven that

electrical energy is stored in a capacitor in the form of a flow of electromagnetic energy circulating in the capacitor. In the same way, it can be assumed that potential gravitational energy is the flows of energy S_φ and S_θ circulating in the volume of the body. The carrier of this energy can be mass currents. This energy changes, turns into an energy flow S_ρ or back during energy exchange between interacting bodies. Apparently, a case is possible when the energy flow, as a mass current. This can be observed as the occurrence of rotation of a body falling on a very massive body.

5. Conclusion

Newton saw the force of attraction of bodies and found a mathematical description of this force. But what happened? The body creates and sends a centripetal force, which is directed into the body! Of course, this is an internally contradictory statement. Newton looked for an explanation for this contradiction. This explanation was demanded by opponents. "I do not invent hypotheses" is an answer to opponents and, most importantly, to myself, so that I could sleep peacefully - because you can't argue with facts.

The followers accepted this force acting towards itself. But then other forces appeared – the centrifugal force and the Coriolis force. There was no explanation for them either. "I do not invent hypotheses, because you can't argue with facts," the followers should have said. But no – they preferred to call these forces non-existent, fictitious. Following Newton, one should have accepted the fact of the existence of these forces [4].

Thus, the internal contradiction of the Law of Universal Gravitation, mentioned above, is removed if we accept the following statements:

1) the force of attraction of the first body to the second body **arises in the first body** and pulls the first body to the second; in this case, the first body transfers energy to the second body;

2) the second body creates a **centrifugal force** in the first body, which depends on the speed of the first body; in this case, the second body transfers energy to the first body.

3) the second body creates a **Coriolis force** in the first body, which depends on the speed of rotation of the first body around its own axis; in this case, the second body transfers energy to the first body (this force is considered in [3]).

These statements make it possible to solve the problem of interaction of many celestial bodies in a completely different way. At the same time, **chaos in these solutions disappears**, chaos that some present

as an achievement of physics [5]. Certainty returns to physics. To show this with real examples is an impossible task for the author (a pensioner, without a team). A sponsor is needed. I would be grateful for offers of cooperation.

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